

Generation Alpha Vocabulary: A Hurdle for English Teachers

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Sheesh, skibidi, rizz, lit, delulu...are these words acceptable to be used by the students in class? The learners of this generation are actually using these new terminologies and left teachers wonder on its meanings since some were not updated with digital world trends. As technology continues to develop, these new words called "Generation Alpha Vocabulary" continue to spread and now learned by the students, worldwide. The impact of technology continues to affect the way students learn and develop their language. In this generation, students are considered as "digital natives" since they grow up along with technology. Moreover, their surroundings revolve with installed Wi-Fi, mobile phones and iPads with updated applications for educational and leisure purposes.

According to studies, teachers are expected to adapt to their students' linguistic development because of their exposure to multimedia and technology. In this sense, there is an inevitable utilization of Generation Alpha vocabulary in oral and writing activities in the classroom. Also, it added to the struggles that teachers are facing everyday as they need to modify their pedagogical approaches to cater the needs of the students in terms of providing engaging learning environment. Aside from adjustment of teaching strategies, a concern was raised on the quality of language learning the students acquire. Teachers noticed that some students are showing poor vocabulary and poor spelling skills despite of acquiring new words from the internet. Even the students are behaving as digitally-cultured, their constant use of digital slangs or social media lingo and shortened expressions are reflections of their limited scope of vocabulary and extreme lexical compression especially in the use of formal language use in speaking and writing tasks. With this, the learners' linguistic development is observed being shifted from achieving formality and precision to emphasizing efficiency and speed.

Teachers and parents have limited awareness of the existence of Generation Alpha words even they are also exposed in technology based on the studies. An additional factor as well the generational gap between the students and the teachers. The so-called intergenerational divide between them is another challenge to cater the learning preferences of the students. Moreover, Generation Alpha vocabulary is not yet acceptable to be used in the academic writing.

These identified challenges and concerns made teachers to think more ways and techniques to ensure that writing and speaking skills of the students in the academic scene must be built with boundaries between the standard and non-standard English usage.

Although Generation Alpha vocabulary is defying the sophistication of language, it still offers positivity for pedagogy such as the development of learners' creativity and self-expression. Teachers who know these new terms also use this for engagement during class discussions as effort to become relatable and relevant. This highlights importance of digital literacy for both students and teachers. With the emergence of these trendy words, teachers must overcome this hurdle through advocating to cease deteriorating language and impede the detrimental impact of technology in terms of language learning and acquisition.

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